

The Impact of Digital Technologies on the Evolution of Linguistic Worldviews

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the peculiarities of the influence of digital technologies on the evolution of linguistic worldviews by analyzing changes in language production, evaluative polarity, and the semantic organization of speech across different types of text environments. A quasi-experimental intergroup comparison was employed, involving Ukrainians interacting with both digital and non-digital informational texts. Quantitative indicators of lexical diversity, utterance length, evaluative markedness, and associative network parameters were used for analysis, along with qualitative analysis of semantic shifts and linguistic norm variability. The results showed that there are systemic differences in language production across discursive environments. Interaction with digital texts is accompanied by a decrease in lexical differentiation, an increase in the evaluative and emotional components of speech, and an increase in the density of associative networks, with a simultaneous narrowing of conceptual detail. The semantic-axiological shifts indicate a transformation in the ways of conceptualizing reality and a stabilization of subjective-evaluative interpretations in linguistic worldviews in the context of digital communication.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Dijital söylem
Dilsel dünya görüşü
Anlamsal kaymalar
Dijital teknoloji
Bilişsel dilbilim

Türkçe Dijital Teknolojilerin Dilsel Dünya Görüşlerinin Evrimi Üzerindeki Etkisi

Özet: Çalışma, dil üretimindeki değişimleri, değerlendirme kutuplaşmasını ve farklı metin ortamlarında söylemin anlamsal örgütlenmesini inceleyerek dijital teknolojilerin dilsel dünya görüşleri üzerindeki etkisinin belirlemeyi amaçlamıştır. Çalışma hem dijital hem de dijital olmayan bilgi içeren metinlerle etkileşime giren Ukraynalıların ana dil kullarımlarını kapsayan kontrollü bir deneysel karşılaştırma olarak yürütülmüştür. Analizde sözcüksel çeşitlilik, ifade uzunluğu, değerlendirme belirginliği ve çağrışımsal ağ parametreleriyle ilgili nicel göstergelerin ile, anlamsal kaymalar ve dilsel norm değişkenliğine yönelik nitel çözümlerler kullanılmıştır. Bulgular, söylemsel ortamlar arasında dil üretiminde sistematik farklılıklar bulunduğunu göstermektedir. Dijital metinlerle etkileşim, sözcüksel farklılaşmada azalma, söylemin değerlendirme ve duygusal bileşenlerinde artış ve çağrışımsal ağların yoğunluğunda artış ile, kavramsal ayrımının eşzamanlı daralmasıyla ilişkilidir. Belirlenen anlamsal-aksiyolojik kaymalar, dijital iletişim bağlamında gerçekliğin kavramsallaştırılma biçimlerinde dönüşümü ve dilsel dünya görüşlerinde öznel-değerlendirici yorumların istikrar kazanmasına işaret etmektedir.

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1. Introduction

The rapid development of digital technologies over the past decades has significantly transformed communication and information processing, directly affecting language practices and mechanisms of meaning formation in the modern sociocultural space (Arıkan & Zorba, 2019; Danylyuk *et al.*, 2023; Pala & Başıbüyük, 2023). In contemporary research, language is viewed not only as a tool for communication but also as a cognitive-social system that reflects ways of conceptualizing, evaluating, and interpreting reality (Panjaitan & Patria, 2024). In this context, digital environments are active agents of language change, shaping new communicative practices and conditions of language production (Salfin *et al.*, 2025).

Cognitive-linguistic approaches demonstrate that the lexical-semantic structures of speech reflect the conceptual models of the language community and form a specific linguistic picture of the world (Renner, 2020). In the digital age, these models are additionally influenced by the active use of digital platforms and network communication, accompanied by changes in the lexical composition and structural organization of speech (Panjaitan & Patria, 2024). Algorithmically mediated communication platforms not only spread linguistic innovations but also stabilize repetitive semantic and evaluative patterns, influencing the structure of language production (Zhang *et al.*, 2024).

In contemporary approaches, language is viewed not only as a reflection of reality but also as a factor in shaping how reality is perceived and evaluated, especially in the context of intensive digital communication (Hatamova, 2025; Danylyuk *et al.*, 2023). Algorithmic personalization of content, characteristic of digital platforms, creates relatively homogeneous information environments that can influence users' language practices and contribute to the consolidation of dominant evaluative models in speech (Stepanova *et al.*, 2023; Walsh, 2020). Despite a significant body of work on digital discourse and the cognitive nature of language, several aspects of the impact of the digital text environment on linguistic worldviews remain insufficiently specified. In particular, most studies focus on individual linguistic or pedagogical aspects of digitalization, without adequately addressing the experimental analysis of cognitive, semantic, and axiological shifts in language production (Renner, 2020; Takahashi, 2025). The question of how interaction with digital and non-digital text environments differently affects the lexical organization of speech, evaluative marking, and the structure of associative connections remains insufficiently studied (Llach, 2023; Li *et al.*, 2025).

The relevance of this study lies in the need for an experimental comparison of language production in interaction with digital and non-digital texts, which are the dominant channels for the formation of evaluative attitudes and semantic structures in modern society. The study aims to identify the peculiarities of the influence of text environment type on speech production, evaluative polarity, and the semantic organization of speech among Ukrainian language speakers. The study aims to analyze differences in lexical diversity, the structure of associative networks, and the nature of evaluative markers across interaction with digital and non-digital discourse, and to outline the cognitively and axiologically relevant shifts that accompany these differences. The scientific novelty of the study lies in the experimental comparison of speech production across digital and non-digital text environments, as well as in the integration of cognitive, semantic, and axiological approaches to the analysis of speech material. The study expands on existing ideas about the influence of text environment type on the lexical organization of speech, evaluative marking, and the structure of associative networks, based on Ukrainian-language material. The practical significance of the work lies

in the possibility of applying the results obtained in studies of contemporary media discourse, digital communication, and educational practices aimed at developing critical digital literacy.

2. Method

This study analyzes the impact of digital technologies on the evolution of linguistic worldviews, focusing on the transformation of lexical-semantic, evaluative, and conceptual structures of linguistic consciousness in the context of digital communication. Within the framework of this work, the concept of the evolution of linguistic worldviews is operationalized as the fixation of synchronous cognitively and axiologically relevant shifts in the conceptual and evaluative structures of linguistic consciousness that reflect the influence of dominant discursive practices of digital communication, rather than as a historical diachronic process. The study was conducted as a controlled experimental study with elements of cognitive-linguistic and psycholinguistic analysis, enabling empirical observation of differences in language production and associative structures across communicative environments.

The methodological basis of the study is the principles of cognitive linguistics, according to which language is a tool for conceptualizing experience and reflecting the mental models formed in social interaction (Cicourel, 1981; Evans, 2012). Within this approach, the linguistic picture of the world is understood as a dynamic system of concepts, semantic fields, and evaluative structures that constantly transforms under the influence of cultural and technological factors (Galantomos, 2019; Jordan, 2025). The study also draws on the principles of cognitive semantics and conceptual metaphor theory, which emphasize the role of metaphorical and metonymic models in the formation of worldview ideas and evaluative attitudes embedded in speech (Kövecses, 2018; Tendahl & Gibbs, 2008). In the digital environment, such models are intensified and standardized by the repetitiveness of discursive patterns and algorithmic content distribution, creating conditions for the stabilization of certain interpretations of reality (Androutsopoulos, 2021; Androutsopoulos, 2024). Of particular methodological significance for this study is the axiological approach to speech analysis, which considers linguistic units as carriers of value and evaluative meanings, socially conditioned ideological positions, and worldview orientations (Bednarek, 2009; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023). The methodological design of the study also takes into account developments in the field of digital discourse analysis, which view online communication as a special type of linguistic interaction with inherent temporal, stylistic, and cognitive characteristics (Đorđević, 2022; Herring, 2018).

2.1. Research Design

Contemporary linguistic research consistently focuses on understanding linguistic meaning through the prism of cognitive structures and mental models that determine the processes of interpreting experience and forming a linguistic picture of the world (Fauzi & Wuryandani, 2025; Renner, 2020). Within cognitive semantics, language is viewed as a system closely linked to categories of thought, conceptual schemes, and culturally conditioned ways of representing reality, which explains the interest in the internal mechanisms of meaning generation (Inoue, 2023; Thompson, 2020).

The scientific literature substantiates the position that the interpretation of linguistic units is grounded in cognitive models that structure linguistic experience and link speech to extra-linguistic reality (Renner, 2020). Such models explain the choice of linguistic forms through figurative, spatial, and conceptual schemes that function in linguistic consciousness and

reflect the accumulated sociocultural experience of the linguistic community (Hatamova, 2025; Nölle *et al.*, 2020). Cognitive lexicology plays an important role in this context, in which lexical units are considered carriers of conceptual content and the result of the interaction among linguistic, psychological, and cultural factors (Galantomos, 2019). Lexicon is understood as a means of recording collective experience and representing the national and cultural specificity of the linguistic picture of the world, thereby allowing language to be analyzed as a dynamic cognitive system (Hatamova, 2025; Jordan, 2025).

A separate area of contemporary research concerns the axiological dimension of language, in which linguistic structures are analyzed as means of encoding values, norms, and evaluative attitudes shaped by a specific sociocultural environment (O'Neill, 2019). In this approach, speech is viewed as an instrument for transmitting ethical and social orientations, ensuring the reproduction and stabilization of value models within the language community (Dupkala & Ambrozy, 2022; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023). Global research pays considerable attention to the relationship between language and worldview, which is interpreted through the prism of linguistic relativity and the structural organization of language systems (Takahashi, 2025). Linguistic diversity is seen as a factor in the formation of different models of conceptualizing and evaluating reality, within which language communities establish their own value priorities (Dupkala & Ambrozy, 2022; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023).

In contemporary scientific discourse, there is a growing interest in analyzing the impact of the digital environment on language practices and discursive forms of communication. Digital platforms are seen as spaces for intensifying linguistic contacts, in which traditional ways of verbalizing experience and evaluating social reality are being rethought (Osadcha, 2023; Panjaitan & Patria, 2024; Sitepu *et al.*, 2024). In such conditions, there is active formation of new linguistic units, abbreviated forms, hybrid constructions, and discursive patterns that shape the linguistic picture of the world (Salfin *et al.*, 2025). The literature pays special attention to the transformation of axiological concepts in digital discourse. Studies show that in online communication, values and evaluative judgments are realized not only verbally but also through multimodal means, particularly visual images, memes, and video content, thereby altering traditional mechanisms of linguistic evaluation (Schafer *et al.*, 2021; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023; Zhang, 2025). Algorithmic mechanisms of content dissemination are analyzed as factors that stabilize repetitive evaluative patterns and reinforce certain worldview attitudes in the digital space (Panjaitan & Patria, 2024; Walsh, 2020).

At the same time, global scientific literature notes the absence of comprehensive interdisciplinary models that would combine cognitive-linguistic analysis of the linguistic picture of the world with research on digital communication. Most works focus either on linguistic structures and value models or on the technical characteristics of the digital environment, without fully revealing the mechanisms by which the linguistic worldview is transformed by digital technologies (Danylyuk *et al.*, 2023; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023). The motivation for this study is the growing influence of digital technologies on contemporary language practices and the need to empirically assess how interaction with the digital text environment affects language production and the evaluative characteristics of discourse. In this context, it is important to identify differences between the processing of digital and neutral informational texts, particularly in terms of evaluative level and semantic shifts. The study aims to identify and quantitatively and qualitatively assess the impact of interaction with the digital text environment on the characteristics of language production and evaluative polarity in the speech of Ukrainian speakers, using an experimental intergroup comparison of digital and non-digital texts. Achieving this goal involves operationalizing the concept of

evaluativeness in speech, determining the role of text type in shaping discursive strategies, and combining automated and expert approaches to analyzing linguistic data. With all these in mind, our research objectives;

1. Analyze differences in participants' language production when interacting with digital texts and neutral non-digital informational texts,
2. Determine the level and direction of evaluative polarity of speech in each experimental group,
3. Identify cognitive and axiological shifts manifested in speech depending on the type of text environment,
4. Compare participants' subjective assessments of text perception with linguistic indicators obtained in the course of the experiment,
5. Perform a comparative characterization of the text stimuli used in the study.

The formulation of hypotheses is based on the provisions of cognitive linguistics, linguoaxiology, and contemporary studies of digital discourse, according to which language production reflects the dominant cognitive and communicative conditions of interaction with the textual environment (Evans, 2012; Bednarek, 2009; Androutsopoulos, 2021). Within these approaches, the digital environment is considered not only as a channel for transmitting information, but also as a factor that modifies the ways of conceptualizing, evaluating, and structuring linguistic experience.

Hypothesis 1. Lexical-structural changes. Interaction with the digital text environment leads to a statistically significant decrease in lexical diversity and a reduction in the average length of utterances in language production, compared with interaction with neutral, non-digital informational texts. Justification: According to the cognitive-discursive approach, the fragmentation and high temporality of digital discourse stimulate the economy of linguistic means and a reduction in the level of conceptual detail (Evans, 2012; Androutsopoulos, 2024).

Hypothesis 2. Axiological intensification. The speech of participants after interaction with digital discourse is characterized by a higher level of evaluative polarity and a greater proportion of explicitly marked evaluative units than speech after interaction with non-digital texts. Justification: Within the linguistic-axiological approach, digital communication is viewed as a context for the intensified expression of positions, emotions, and value judgments, leading to the dominance of evaluative components over neutral-descriptive ones (Bednarek, 2009; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023).

Hypothesis 3. Semantic organization and associative networks. Associative networks formed after interaction with the digital text environment have higher density but lower conceptual differentiation than those formed after interaction with non-digital texts. Justification: Cognitive semantics and digital discourse studies indicate a tendency to activate high-frequency, generalized concepts in network communication, leading to densification of associative connections while simultaneously narrowing conceptual diversity (Kövecses, 2018; Androutsopoulos, 2021).

Hypothesis 4. The connection between subjective perception and linguistic production. Differences in the subjective perception of digital and non-digital texts are accompanied by systematic differences in the evaluative markedness and lexical organization of language production, which indicates the indirect role of text environment perception in language transformations. Justification: According to cognitive-pragmatic approaches, the evaluation

of text as a communicative object directly influences the choice of linguistic strategies and the degree of subjectivization of speech (Bednarek, 2008; Thompson et al., 2020).

2.2. Participants

The study was a controlled experimental study with an intergroup design, comparing linguistic and cognitive indicators across different types of text environments. The experiment aimed to record differences in language production, associative connections, and evaluative speech structures following interaction with digital and non-digital discourse.

Participants were recruited through open online recruitment from July 5, 2025, to August 5, 2025. Invitations to participate in the study were distributed through thematic online communities on WhatsApp focused on discussing digital communication, media consumption, contemporary culture, and everyday language practices. In particular, open groups dedicated to digital literacy, online content analysis, social networks, and media trends were involved. A total of 97 people responded to the invitation, agreed to participate in the study, and completed an online questionnaire on their language and digital profile (Appendix 1). The questionnaire developed by the authors included sections to record the intensity of digital platform use, the types of online content consumed, and language preferences in the digital environment, in particular, the identification of Ukrainian as the main language of daily communication.

The final composition of participants was determined through targeted stratification, with predefined inclusion criteria. At the screening stage, 33 respondents were excluded for the following reasons: irregular use of digital platforms (less than 2 hours per day), dominance of a language other than Ukrainian in daily communication, professional linguistic or philological education, and incomplete questionnaire. The final sample consisted of 64 participants ($n = 64$; 36 women, 28 men) aged 19 to 40 ($M = 26.9$) who actively used Ukrainian as their main language of everyday communication and had stable experience with digital platforms. The inclusion criteria were regular use of digital communication environments (at least 2 hours daily), no diagnosed cognitive or speech disorders, and no specialized linguistic training. The participants in the final sample were randomly divided into two equal groups.

Participants in the first group (Group 1) worked with neutral non-digital informational texts adapted from popular science and reference publications available through open scientific and educational archives and databases (in particular, Google Scholar). These texts did not belong to digital public communication formats such as social networks or online news platforms. These sources were also chosen because they used academic, standardized language focused on informative presentation and limited use of personalized and evaluative language. Participants in the second group (Group 2) interacted with texts representative of contemporary digital discourse, including excerpts from online platform news feeds and short posts from publicly accessible social network accounts (Instagram, X/Twitter, Facebook). The selection of digital materials was made with established formats of public online communication in mind and limited to formally homogeneous text units, without user comments or multimodal elements. The materials of both groups were standardized in terms of volume and subject matter; the topics covered neutral areas of everyday knowledge. During the selection process, a preliminary linguistic screening was conducted to ensure a comparable level of lexical complexity and to eliminate potentially sensitive or provocative content.

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection was carried out in two stages: pre-experimental questioning and the main experimental block. Pre-experimental questioning was conducted online via Google Forms. The data were used to screen participants for inclusion criteria and to describe the sample profile. The experimental tasks were implemented on the Qualtrics platform, which ensured standardized presentation of materials, automatic recording of completion times, and a unified task order.

Within the experiment, each participant interacted with three text stimuli. Participants in Group 1 worked with neutral non-digital informational texts, while participants in Group 2 interacted with texts representative of contemporary digital public communication. After working through each text, participants performed three types of experimental tasks: a text production task (a short written summary of the main topic of the text), an associative test (free generation of associations with predefined key concepts), and text evaluation on a Likert scale according to the parameters of reliability, objectivity, information load, and trust in the source. The experimental tasks were developed by the authors (Appendix 2) based on classical psycholinguistic methods of free association aimed at studying semantic connections and cognitive accessibility of concepts (Nelson *et al.*, 2004), as well as approaches to discourse analysis and pragmatic evaluation of texts used in corpus and functional linguistics (Bednarek, 2008; Biber *et al.*, 1999).

Quantitative analysis in the study involved formalized measurement of lexical, evaluative, and semantic parameters of linguistic material based on automated computational methods. Lexical characteristics were determined using type-token ratios, lexical diversity indices, and lexeme frequency indicators in Python (NLTK, spaCy, and pandas). The evaluative polarity of the texts was calculated using the VADER tool as an auxiliary automated analysis tool. The results were supplemented by manual expert review of part of the data, taking into account the specifics of the Ukrainian language and the contextual meaning of linguistic units, thereby ensuring quality control and the correct interpretation of automatically generated indicators. Semantic shifts were analyzed through co-occurrence networks of lexemes and vector representations of words (FastText). Two independent experts coded associative data into categories (concepts, evaluation, emotions, technological markers). The coding agreement was $\kappa \geq 0.85$. Based on the coding, the frequency of association categories and the structure of associative networks were determined for the two groups. Statistical analysis was performed in R 4.3.1 (packages lme4, emmeans, psych). To compare intergroup differences, the t-test for independent samples was used; when the distributions of quantitative indicators were nonnormal, the Mann-Whitney U-test was used. The χ^2 test was used to analyze categorical data. Additionally, linear mixed models were used to account for the random effects of participants and stimuli. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

The study was conducted on a sample of active digital platform users so that the results may be less relevant to groups with lower levels of digital engagement. Online recruitment via WhatsApp could have caused self-selection bias, which was minimized by strict inclusion and exclusion criteria for professional linguists, as well as by matching the sample profile to the research topic. The study is cross-sectional and captures the cognitive effects of interaction with different types of discourse, rather than the historical dynamics of linguistic worldview evolution. The analysis was limited to the textual component of digital communication without multimodality. Another limitation of the study is that only

participants who predominantly used Ukrainian in everyday communication were included in the sample, limiting the generalizability of the results to language communities with other dominant languages or with a different language organization. The study was conducted in accordance with generally accepted international ethical standards. Participants were informed about the purpose, procedures, and specifics of the study and voluntarily agreed to participate. Respondents' personal information was not collected, and the study results were anonymized through coding. The collected materials were stored on secure media with limited access for members of the research team.

3. Findings

To test the hypotheses put forward in the study, a system of quantitative and qualitative indicators of language production was used. In particular, hypothesis 1 was tested by analyzing lexical diversity and average utterance length, which enabled assessment of the degree of speech structural complexity in the context of interaction with different types of text environments. Hypothesis 2 was operationalized through indicators of evaluative polarity and the frequency of explicitly marked evaluative units. To test hypothesis 3, an analysis of associative networks was conducted, focusing on their density and level of conceptual differentiation. Hypothesis 4 was tested by comparing indicators of subjective perception of texts with characteristics of speech production.

Figure 1. Comparison of lexical diversity indicators (type-token index) in two groups (with standard deviation errors)

The results of the text production analysis showed statistically significant differences between the groups that interacted with digital and non-digital text environments. Participants in the digital discourse group (Group 2) demonstrated lower lexical diversity than those in the neutral informational text group (Group 1). The mean type-token index in Group 2 was $M = 0.43$ ($SD = 0.06$), while in Group 1 it was $M = 0.49$ ($SD = 0.05$). The difference was statistically significant ($t(62) = 4.12$; $p < 0.001$) (Figure 1). Analysis of the average length of utterances also showed that discourse type influences language production. The texts of Group 2 participants had a shorter average sentence length ($M = 11.6$ words; $SD = 2.3$) than those of Group 1 ($M = 14.2$; $SD = 2.7$), indicating a tendency toward more fragmented expression after interaction with the digital environment. The difference between the groups is statistically significant ($t(62) = 3.98$; $p < 0.001$). A quantitative analysis of the frequency of functional and content words showed that the proportion of generalized and vague nominations increased in the speech of Group 2 participants. At the same time, the texts of Group 1 contained a greater number of specific and terminologically stable units. The results

indicate a systematic influence of the type of textual environment on the formal parameters of speech production. The quantitative indicators obtained are interpreted as relative indicators of intergroup differences reflecting the influence of the type of discursive environment, rather than as absolute characteristics of individual speech style.

The results of the evaluative polarity analysis showed clear differences between the groups depending on the type of text environment. In the language production of Group 2 participants, a higher level of overall evaluativeness was recorded compared to Group 1. The average value of the integral indicator of evaluative polarity in Group 2 was $M = 0.21$ ($SD = 0.09$), while in Group 1 it was $M = 0.12$ ($SD = 0.07$). The difference between the groups is statistically significant ($U = 312.5$; $p < 0.01$) (Fig. 2). Automated evaluative polarity scores obtained using the VADER tool were used as an auxiliary means of comparative analysis and are interpreted as relative indicators of intergroup differences, taking into account further expert verification of the linguistic context.

Structural analysis of evaluative markers showed that participants in the digital group used explicit positive and negative evaluative units more often, particularly adjectives and adverbs with a pronounced subjective meaning. In contrast, neutral descriptive constructions prevailed in the speech of Group 1. The share of evaluative lexemes in Group 2 texts was 18.4%, while in Group 1 it was 11.2%. Analysis of associative reactions confirmed this trend. In the associative networks of Group 2 participants, evaluative and emotionally charged categories were more frequently recorded, while in Group 1, conceptual and descriptive associations dominated. The consistency of expert coding of associative data was high ($\kappa = 0.87$), indicating the stability of the identified patterns. The results indicate a strengthening of the axiological component of speech following interaction with digital discourse, along with a shift in the balance between neutral information and subjective interpretation of the text. Subjective assessments of texts obtained using Likert scales are consistent with linguistic indicators: texts that participants rated as less objective and less neutral were accompanied by increased evaluative markedness and decreased lexical differentiation in speech production.

Figure 2. Average values of evaluative polarity indicators in the speech production of participants from both groups

Analysis of associative data revealed systemic differences in the structure of semantic connections between groups. Participants who interacted with the digital text environment (Group 2) demonstrated a higher density of associative networks but a lower level of

conceptual differentiation compared to Group 1. The average number of associations per stimulus in Group 2 was $M = 6.3$ ($SD = 1.4$), while in Group 1 it was $M = 5.1$ ($SD = 1.2$); the difference was statistically significant ($t(62) = 3.47$; $p < 0.01$). At the same time, the qualitative composition of associative reactions differed significantly. In Group 2, associations of a general nature prevailed, as did reactions with evaluative and emotional semantics. Participants more often produced associations related to personal interpretation, reactions of approval or rejection, and technological markers.

Table 1.

Comparative Structure of Associative Networks

Indicator	Group 1	Group 2
Number of unique nodes (lexemes)	124	96
Average link density	0.21	0.34
Proportion of evaluatively marked lexemes	18	41
Dominance of emotional clusters	low	high

In contrast, the associative networks of Group 1 were characterized by a greater proportion of subject-logical and definitional connections focused on clarifying the content and conceptual characteristics of stimulus units. Analysis of lexeme co-occurrence networks confirmed the presence of semantic shifts in the digital group: in Group 2, there was an increase in the frequency of central, high-frequency nodes with a wide semantic radius, while in Group 1, the networks had a more branched structure with clearly defined thematic clusters. The results indicate that the semantic organization of linguistic material varies across discursive environments. The comparative structure of associative networks in the two groups is presented in Table 1. The generalized differences in language production across textual environments are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Generalized Differences in Language Production Depending on the Type of Text Environment

Type of text environment	Lexical organization of speech	Evaluative markedness	Semantic organization
Digital	Decrease in lexical diversity, reduction in average utterance length	Higher level of evaluative polarity, an increase in the proportion of explicitly marked evaluative units	Higher density of associative networks at a lower level of conceptual differentiation
Non-digital	Higher lexical diversity, greater average length of utterances	Prevalence of neutral-descriptive components	Lower density of associative networks with a higher level of conceptual differentiation

The analysis of contact-induced language deviations showed that interaction with the digital text environment is associated with an increase in the number of uncoded and variable language realizations in written production. The texts of Group 2 participants more often contained atypical semantic extensions and simplified syntactic constructions, reflecting the influence of templated digital discursive practices. The average number of such deviations in Group 2 was 2.8 per text ($SD = 1.1$), while in Group 1 it was 1.6 ($SD = 0.9$); the difference was statistically significant ($U = 298.0$; $p < 0.01$). The total share of texts with recorded non-coded linguistic realizations in Group 2 was 41%, while in Group 1 it was 23%. Expert coding of these phenomena showed high consistency ($\kappa = 0.85$), which indicates the stability of the identified patterns. The data obtained confirm that the type of text environment affects not only the formal and evaluative parameters of speech, but also the degree of linguistic norm variability in the context of digital communication.

To ensure a controlled comparison of language processing across different discursive environments, the study used two types of text stimuli: non-digital (traditional) informational texts and digital texts from public online communication. The materials were selected based on their functional purpose, linguistic and stylistic characteristics, and degree of evaluativeness. The comparative characteristics of the non-digital and digital texts used in the study are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Comparative Characteristics of Non-digital and Digital Texts

Comparison Parameter	Non-digital (traditional) texts	Digital texts
Type of discourse	Informational–academic	Public digital
Source	Popular science and reference publications (e.g., Google Scholar)	Social networks, online platforms, and comments
Communicative purpose	Informing, explaining	Expressing position, evaluation, & interaction
Style of speech	Standardized, neutral	Colloquial, hybrid
Presence of personalized narrative	Absent	Often present
Level of evaluativeness	Minimal or absent	Increased
Emotional marking	Low	Medium or high
Orientation toward the addressee	General reader	Specific or imaginary audience
Type of linguistic norm	Codified literary language	Variable, with elements of spoken language
Degree of discursive standardization	Low	High
Level of algorithmic influence on text form	Absent	Indirect (through platform formats)
Expected cognitive processing	Analytical, content-oriented	Fast, fragmentary, evaluation-oriented

A comparison of the characteristics of textual stimuli reveals a fundamental difference between the conditions of language processing in non-digital and digital discursive environments. Non-digital texts created a cognitively neutral background, minimizing the influence of emotional and evaluative factors, while digital texts represented the natural environment of modern online communication with its inherent subjectivity and expressiveness. This approach enabled clear isolation of the influence of discourse type on participants' linguistic and cognitive indicators and ensured the validity of subsequent intergroup comparisons.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The results of the study allow us to interpret the recorded changes in language production as a consequence of the systemic influence of digital technologies on the evolution of linguistic worldviews. In this context, the data generally confirm hypothesis 1, which posits that interaction with the digital text environment is associated with a decrease in lexical diversity and a reduction in the average length of utterances. The observed decrease in lexical diversity and average sentence length in the speech of participants who interacted with digital texts of public online communication is consistent with recent studies linking the fragmentation and high dynamism of digital discourse with the formation of concise and less

differentiated linguistic structures (Balci & Kartal, 2021; Chen, 2022). The increase in the proportion of generalized nominations and the reduction in the number of terminologically stable units in the texts of the digital group indicate a shift from an analytical to a more interpretative mode of linguistic coding. Similar trends are described in works devoted to the axiological transformations of language in the context of globalization and digital communication, where speech functions as an instrument of social positioning and evaluation (Dupkala & Ambrozy, 2022; Stepanova *et al.*, 2023).

The analysis of evaluative polarity indicates a strengthening of the axiological component of speech in digital communication. Thus, hypothesis 2 finds empirical confirmation, since the increased level of evaluativeness in the speech of participants who worked with social media and online platforms is consistent with the findings of linguistic axiological studies that consider digital space as an environment for the active expression of positions, emotions, and value judgments (Hatamova, 2025; Schafer *et al.*, 2021). A comparison of the data obtained with the results of other authors allows us to consider the recorded axiological shifts as a reflection of broader sociocultural processes. Research in the field of digital education shows that digital technologies increase engagement and motivation while requiring adaptation to users' cognitive and critical needs (Danylyuk, 2023; Lin *et al.*, 2023). In this sense, the results of the study refine previous conclusions, pointing to the structural predominance of evaluative components of speech in conditions of limited involvement of mechanisms of deep analytical understanding.

The higher density of associative networks, accompanied by a simultaneous decrease in conceptual differentiation, indicates the activation of broader, less structured semantic fields in the digital environment. The results are consistent with hypothesis 3, which posits that digital communication contributes to the formation of dense yet conceptually simplified associative structures. A similar effect is described in studies of the cognitive consequences of digital communication, which emphasize the dominance of high-frequency, general concepts (Androutsopoulos, 2024). The increase in the number of evaluative and emotionally marked associations is also consistent with data on the accelerated spread and standardization of evaluative models within online communities (Pascual, 2018; Urena *et al.*, 2019). The change, like semantic connections in network speech, corresponds to observations of algorithmically mediated repetition of semantic patterns in social media, where central nodes with a wide semantic radius dominate (Chonmurunova & Kulpoldieva, 2025; Duncker, 2017). In a broader theoretical context, such shifts can be understood through the prism of the socially conditioned nature of linguistic cognition, which holds that linguistic structures are formed in close connection with communicative practices and cultural models of interaction (Inoue, 2023; Thompson, 2020).

The results of the study indicate consistency between subjective perceptions of texts and characteristics of speech production, partially confirming hypothesis 4. Similar observations are presented in studies of digital discourse, which emphasize the role of users' perceptual and evaluative attitudes in shaping language strategies and the degree of subjectivization of speech (Androutsopoulos, 2021; Inoue, 2023; Thompson *et al.*, 2020). This allows us to consider the perception of digital content as a factor that mediates the choice of evaluative and lexical strategies, without reducing these relationships to a direct statistical dependence.

In a broader theoretical context, the results obtained clarify cognitive linguistics' position on the dependence of linguistic conceptualization on the type of communicative environment. The identified shifts in lexical organization, evaluative marking, and semantic structure of

speech indicate that the digital text environment is not only a channel for transmitting information, but also a factor that systematically modifies the cognitive and axiological parameters of language production. The results obtained complement contemporary ideas about the socially conditioned nature of linguistic cognition in the context of digital communication. At the same time, the results of the study require careful interpretation in light of several limitations, in particular the written nature of language production, the experimental conditions, and the limited range of digital texts used. These factors do not allow for automatic extrapolation to all types of digital discourse. Promising areas for further research include analyzing oral speech in the digital environment, comparing different genres of online communication, and expanding the material to include other languages and cultural contexts.

The results show that interaction with digital technologies is accompanied by systemic shifts in language production and the semantic-evaluative organization of linguistic worldviews. The digital discursive environment correlates with decreased lexical differentiation, increased evaluative marking, and a tendency toward generalized and fragmented linguistic realizations, reflecting the specifics of cognitive information processing in digital communication. Analysis of associative networks has shown changes akin to semantic connections: an increase in network density has been observed, accompanied by a simultaneous narrowing of conceptual diversity, indicating a reformatting of the conceptual structures of linguistic consciousness. The identified axiological shifts are manifested in the stable dominance of subjective-evaluative interpretations over neutral-descriptive ones, which have consequences for the formation of collective linguistic representations of reality.

The novelty of the study lies in the empirical recording of cognitively and axiologically relevant parameters of linguistic worldview transformation in a synchronous dimension, and in the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods of digital speech analysis. The practical significance of the results lies in their potential to analyze contemporary media discourses and to develop strategies for language education and critical reading in the digital environment. At the same time, the interpretation of the data is limited by the sample composition, the analysis's textual focus, and the absence of a multimodal component. Further research should focus on interlingual comparisons, the involvement of different types of digital platforms, and the analysis of the long-term effects of digital communication on the dynamics of linguistic worldviews.

Ethical Statement

Ethical permission for this study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Kyiv National Linguistic University (Department of Germanic and Roman Languages), in accordance with institutional research regulations with the decision number of F3/2026. Also,

Informed Consent

Written informed consent form was obtained from each participant.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. For privacy reasons, the data from this study are not publicly available.

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Appendix 1. Questionnaire on the Language and Digital Profile of Participants

1. General Information

1. Age: 18–20 21–25 26–30 31–35 36–40 Over 40
2. Gender: Female Male Prefer not to say
3. Level of Education: Secondary Incomplete higher Higher Postgraduate
4. Main Field of Activity: Education Professional (non-linguistic) Not working Other: _____

2. Language Profile

5. Primary Language of Daily Communication: Ukrainian Other: _____
6. Frequency of Using Ukrainian: Always Mostly Sometimes Rarely
7. Domains of Ukrainian Use: Daily communication Education Professional Online Other
8. Linguistic/Philological Education: Yes No

3. Use of Digital Platforms

9. Daily Time in Digital Communication: <1h 1–2h 2–4h >4h
10. Platforms Used: Social media Messengers News Video Other
11. Purpose: Information Communication Entertainment Professional/Educational Mixed

4. Language Practices in Digital Environment

12. Language Used Online: Ukrainian Other: _____ Depends
13. Style: Neutral Emotional Mixed
14. Influence: None Slight Significant Very significant
15. Simplified Language Use: Yes Mostly yes Rather no No

5. Self-Assessment of Digital Text Perception

16. Rate (1–5): Reliable / Objective / Informative / Persuasive
17. Critical Evaluation Frequency: Always Often Sometimes Rarely

Appendix 2. Experimental tasks

Task 1. Text production: Briefly summarize the main topic of the text you have read in your own words. Try to convey the meaning of the text as you understand it. The answer should be 5–7 sentences long.

Task 2. Associative test: Read the words below and write down all the associations that come to mind for each of them. Write down the first words or phrases that come to mind. There is no limit to the number of associations.

List of stimulus units:

- Information
- Source
- Reliability
- Evaluation

Task 3. Subjective evaluation of the text: Please evaluate the text on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 means “completely disagree” and 5 means “completely agree.”

Assess how much the material you have read is:

- reliable
- objective
- informative
- influential and persuasive

Please carefully repeat the entire set of tasks after reading each subsequent text, following the same procedure. All tasks must be completed separately for each text, without generalizing the answers between different materials.